

Independent Open Irredundant Colorings of Graphs

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Abstract: A vertex $v \in V - S$ is an external private neighbor of u with respect to S if v is adjacent to u but no other vertex in S . A set $S \subseteq V$ is *open irredundant* if every vertex in S has an external private neighbor with respect to S . A set S is called an *independent open irredundant set* or *ioir-set* if S is an independent set and every vertex in S has an external private neighbor with respect to S . An *independent open irredundant coloring* of a graph G is a partition of $V(G)$ into *independent open irredundant* sets. In this paper, we introduce the study of *independent open irredundant colorings* of graphs.

Key Words: Independence, irredundance, open irredundant coloring, independent open irredundant coloring, Smarandachely k -independent open irredundant set.

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§1. Introduction

By a graph $G = (V, E)$ we mean a finite, undirected graph without loops or multiple edges. The order and size of G are denoted by n and m respectively. For graph theoretic terminology we refer to Chartrand and Lesniak [2].

Domination is a well studied concept in graph theory. For an excellent treatment of fundamentals of domination we refer to the book by Haynes et al. [6]. Several advanced topics in domination are given in the book edited by Haynes et al. [7].

The neighbourhood of a vertex $x \in V(G)$ in the graph G is denoted by $N(x)$ and the closed neighbourhood $\{x\} \cup N(x)$ by $N[x]$. If X is a subset of $V(G)$, then $N[X] = \bigcup_{x \in X} N[x]$ and the subgraph induced by X is denoted by $G[X]$.

In 1999, Cockayne [3] introduced the study of a large class of generalized irredundant sets in graphs. Each type of a generalized irredundant set $S \subset V$ is defined by the types of private neighbors (i.e self, internal or external) that each vertex in the set must have. A subset S of V in a graph G is said to be *independent* if no two vertices in S are adjacent. Let $u \in S$. A vertex $v \in V - S$ is an external private neighbor of u with respect to S if v is adjacent to u but no other vertex in S . A vertex $u \in S$ is its own private neighbor if it is not adjacent to any vertex in S . A set S is called *irredundant* if every vertex in S is either its own private neighbor or has an external private neighbor, with respect to S . A set S is called an *independent open*

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irredundant set or *ioir-set* if S is an independent set and every vertex in S has an external private neighbor.

Generally, a set S is called a *Smarandachely k -independent open irredundant set* if there is a subset $V_0 \subset V$ with $|V_0| = k$ such that S is an independent set and every vertex in S has an external private neighbor in V_0 . Clearly, if $V_0 = V$, a Smarandachely $|G|$ -independent open irredundant set is nothing else but an *ioir-set*.

In [3], Cockayne identifies 12 types of generalised irredundant sets the properties of which are hereditary. Perhaps the most interesting of these are the *ioir-sets*. One can therefore define $ioir(G)$ to equal the minimum size of a maximal *ioir-set* and $IOIR(G)$ to equal the maximum size of an *ioir-set*. These generalised irredundant sets are also studied by Finbow in [5] and Cockayne and Finbow in [4].

If a collection of edges between two sets of vertices, say A and B , define a bijection between A and B , then we call such a perfect matching a bijective matching.

A proper k -coloring of a graph G is a partition $\pi = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_k\}$ of V into k non-empty independent sets. The chromatic number $\chi(G)$ equals the minimum integer k for which G has a k -coloring. More generally given a property P concerning subsets of V , a P -coloring is a partition $\pi = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_k\}$ of V into sets, such that each V_i has the property P . If the property P is independence, the P -coloring is the usual coloring and if the property P is domination, the corresponding P -coloring gives the concept of domatic partition. Haynes et al. [8] introduced the concept of irredundant colorings and open irredundant colorings of graphs. Arumugam et al. [1] initiate a study of open irredundant colorings and obtain some results on irredundant colorings and open irredundant colorings. Motivated by the work on [1,8], we initiate a study of *independent open irredundant colorings*. An *independent open irredundant coloring* of a graph G is a partition of V into nonempty independent open irredundant sets. The *independent open irratic number* is the minimum order of an independent open irredundant coloring of G , and it is denoted by $\chi_{ioir}(G)$. In section 2, we obtain some results on independent open irredundant colorings. A study of harmonious, achromatic coloring on middle graph, central graph, total graph, line graph of various classes of graphs can be found in [10, 11, 12, 13]. In Section 3, we investigate the *independent open irratic number* for the middle graph, central graph, total graph, line graph of double star graph families.

We need the following theorems.

Theorem 1.1([6]) *If a graph G has no isolated vertices, then G has a minimum dominating set which is also open irredundant.*

Theorem 1.2([8]) *For any graph G , $n/IR(G) \leq \chi_{ir}(G) \leq n - IR(G) + 1$.*

Observation 1.3([1]) *Since any *oir*-coloring of G is an *ir*-coloring of G , it follows that $\chi_{ir}(G) \leq \chi_{oir}(G)$.*

Theorem 1.4([8]) *For any graph G , $\chi_{oir}(G) = 2$ if and only if $V(G)$ can be partitioned into two subsets V_1 and V_2 such that there exists a bijective matching between V_1 and V_2 .*

Throughout, we assume that G is a graph without isolated vertices.

§2. Independent Open Irredundant Colorings

Observation 2.1 Since any *ioir*-coloring of G is an *oir*-coloring and χ -coloring of G , it follows that $\chi_{ir}(G) \leq \chi_{oir}(G) \leq \chi_{ioir}(G)$ and $\chi_{ir}(G) \leq \chi(G) \leq \chi_{ioir}(G)$.

Observation 2.1 Since $V(G)$ is not an *ioir*-set of G , it follows that $2 \leq \chi_{ioir}(G) \leq n$.

Theorem 2.3 For any graph G , $\chi_{ioir}(G) = 2$ if and only if $V(G)$ can be partitioned into two independent subsets V_1 and V_2 such that there exists a bijective matching between V_1 and V_2 .

Proof The proof follows from Theorem 1.4. \square

Theorem 2.4 Let G be a graph of order n . Then $\chi_{ioir}(G) = n$ if and only if for any independent set $S \subset V$, there exists $v, w \in S$ such that $N(v) \subseteq N(w)$ or $N(w) \subseteq N(v)$.

Proof Assume that $\chi_{ioir}(G) = n$. Suppose there is an independent set $S \subset V$ such that $N(v) \not\subseteq N(w)$ and $N(w) \not\subseteq N(v) \forall v, w \in S$. Then there exists a vertex $z_1 \in N(v)$ such that z_1 is not adjacent to w and there exists a vertex $z_2 \in N(w)$ such that z_2 is not adjacent to v . Hence $\{v, w\}$ is an *ioir*-set and $IOIR(G) \geq 2$. Therefore $\chi_{ioir}(G) \leq n - 1$ which is a contradiction. The converse is obvious. \square

Observation 2.5 For any complete graph K_n and complete bipartite graph $K_{m,n}$, we have $\chi_{ioir}(K_n) = n$ and $\chi_{ioir}(K_{m,n}) = m + n$.

Observation 2.6 For any tree T , $\chi_{ioir}(T) = n$ if and only if T is a star.

Theorem 2.7 For the path $P_n = (v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n)$, we have $\chi_{ioir}(P_n) = 3$.

Proof Let $V_1 = \{v_1, v_4, v_7, v_{10}, \dots\}$, $V_2 = \{v_2, v_5, v_8, v_{11}, \dots\}$, $V_3 = \{v_3, v_6, v_9, v_{12}, \dots\}$.

Clearly $\{V_1, V_2, V_3\}$ is a partition of $V(G)$ into independent open irredundant sets. Hence $\chi_{ioir}(P_n) \leq 3$. By Theorem 2.3, $\chi_{ioir}(P_n) \geq 3$ and so $\chi_{ioir}(P_n) = 3$. \square

Theorem 2.8 For the cycle $C_n = (v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n)$, we have

$$\chi_{ioir}(C_n) = \begin{cases} 4 & \text{if } n = 4 \text{ or } n = 7 \\ 3 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

Proof We can easily observe that $\chi_{ioir}(C_4) = 4$. We now prove that $\chi_{ioir}(C_n) = 3$ for $n \neq 4$ or 7 . By Theorem 2.3, $\chi_{ioir}(C_n) \geq 3$. Now we consider three cases.

Case 1. $n \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$.

Let $V_1 = \{v_1, v_4, v_7, v_{10}, \dots, v_{n-2}\}$, $V_2 = \{v_2, v_5, v_8, v_{11}, \dots, v_{n-1}\}$ and $V_3 = \{v_3, v_6, v_9, v_{12}, \dots, v_n\}$. Clearly $\{V_1, V_2, V_3\}$ is a partition of $V(G)$ into independent open irredundant sets since any three consecutive vertices in the cycle receives distinct colors. Hence $\chi_{ioir}(C_n) \leq 3$.

Case 2. $n \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$.

Let $V_1 = \{v_1, v_3, v_6, v_8, v_{11}, v_{14}, v_{17}, \dots, v_{l-3}, v_l, v_{l+3}, \dots, v_{n-2}\}$, $V_2 = \{v_2, v_4, v_7, v_9, v_{12},$

$v_{15}, v_{18}, \dots, v_{l-3}, v_l, v_{l+3}, \dots, v_{n-1}\}$, $V_3 = \{v_5, v_{10}, v_{13}, v_{16}, v_{19}, \dots, v_{l-3}, v_l, v_{l+3}, \dots, v_n\}$. We now prove that $\{V_1, V_2, V_3\}$ is a partition of $V(G)$ into independent open irredundant sets. Clearly the sets V_i , $i = 1, 2, 3$ are independent. Hence it is enough to prove that every vertex in the set V_i has an external private neighbour with respect to V_i , $i = 1, 2, 3$. Note that v_1, v_5, v_6 are the external private neighbors of v_2, v_4, v_7 respectively and v_n, v_4, v_7 and v_{10} are the external private neighbors of v_1, v_3, v_8 and v_9 respectively. All other remaining vertices v_i have external private neighbor v_{i-1} .

Case 3. $n \equiv 2(\text{mod}3)$.

Let $V_1 = \{v_1, v_4, v_7, v_{10}, \dots, v_{n-1}\}$, $V_2 = \{v_2, v_5, v_8, v_{11}, \dots, v_n\}$ and $V_3 = \{v_3, v_6, v_9, v_{12}, \dots, v_{n-2}\}$. Since v_2, v_{n-1}, v_{n-2} are the external private neighbors of v_1, v_n, v_{n-1} respectively and remaining vertices v_i have external private neighbor v_{i+1} , $\{V_1, V_2, V_3\}$ is a partition of $V(G)$ into independent open irredundant sets. Hence $\chi_{ioir}(C_n) \leq 3$. Now we prove that $\chi_{ioir}(C_7) = 4$. Since any independent open irredundant set of C_7 has at most two vertices, minimum four colors are required to color the vertices of C_7 . Let $V_1 = \{v_1, v_3\}$, $V_2 = \{v_2, v_6\}$, $V_3 = \{v_3, v_5\}$ and $V_4 = \{v_7\}$. Clearly $\{V_1, V_2, V_3, V_4\}$ is an *ioir*-coloring of C_7 . Hence $\chi_{ioir}(C_7) = 4$. \square

Proposition 2.9 For any graph G , $n/IOIR(G) \leq \chi_{ioir}(G) \leq n-IOIR(G)+1$, where $IOIR(G)$ is the upper independent open irredundance number of G .

Proof Let $\chi_{ioir}(G) = k$. Let $\{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_k\}$ be an *ioir*-coloring of G . Since $|V_i| \leq IOIR(G)$, it follows that $n = \sum_{i=1}^k |V_i| \leq k \cdot IOIR(G)$. Hence $n/IOIR(G) \leq \chi_{ioir}(G)$. Now, let S be an independent open irredundant set of G with $|S| = IOIR(G)$. Then $\{S\} \cup \{\{v\} : v \in V - S\}$ is an *ioir*-coloring of G . Hence $\chi_{ioir}(G) \leq n - IOIR(G) + 1$. \square

Theorem 2.10 Let G be a connected graph with $\delta = 1$ and let r denote the maximum number of leaves adjacent to a support vertex v of G . Then $\chi_{ioir}(G) \geq r + 2$.

Proof Let v_1, v_2, \dots, v_r be the leaves adjacent to v . Since any independent open irredundant set in G contains at most one of the leaves v_i , the result follows. \square

Observation 2.11 Let $T \neq K_{1,n}$ be any tree and let r denote the maximum number of leaves adjacent to a support vertex v of T . Then $\chi_{ioir}(T) \geq r + 2$.

§3. IOIR-Coloring on Double Star Graph Families

In this section we investigate the independent open irratic number for the central graph, middle graph, total graph, line graph of star graph $K_{1,n}$ and double star graph $K_{1,n,n}$.

The central graph $C(G)$ of a graph G is formed by adding an extra vertex on each edge of G , and then joining each pair of vertices of the original graph which were previously non-adjacent.

Let G be a graph with vertex set $V(G)$ and edge set $E(G)$. The middle graph of G , denoted by $M(G)$ is defined as follows. The vertex set of $M(G)$ is $V(G) \cup E(G)$. Two vertices x, y in the vertex set $M(G)$ are adjacent in $M(G)$ in case one of the following holds: (i) x, y are in $E(G)$ and x, y are adjacent in G . (ii) x is in $V(G)$, y is in $E(G)$, and x, y are incident in G .

The total graph of G has vertex set $V(G) \cup E(G)$, and edges joining all elements of this vertex set which are adjacent or incident in G .

The line graph of G denoted by $L(G)$ is the graph with vertices are the edges of G with two vertices of $L(G)$ adjacent whenever the corresponding edges of G are adjacent.

A star is a complete bipartite graph $K_{1,m}$ with $m \geq 2$, and the unique vertex v of this star of degree m is called the center.

Double star $K_{1,n,n}$ is a tree obtained from the star $K_{1,n}$ by adding a new pendant edge of the existing n pendant vertices. It has $2n + 1$ vertices and $2n$ edges. Let $V(K_{1,n,n}) = \{v\} \cup \{v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n\} \cup \{u_1, u_2, \dots, u_n\}$ and $E(K_{1,n,n}) = \{e_1, e_2, \dots, e_n\} \cup \{s_1, s_2, \dots, s_n\}$.

Proposition 3.1 *For any star graph $K_{1,n}$, we have*

- (i) $\chi_{ioir}(M(K_{1,n})) = n + 2$;
- (ii) $\chi_{ioir}(C(K_{1,n})) = n + 1$;
- (iii) $\chi_{ioir}(T(K_{1,n})) = n + 2$;
- (iv) $\chi_{ioir}(L(K_{1,n})) = n$.

Proof (i) By the definition of middle graph, each edge vv_i in $K_{1,n}$ is subdivided by the vertex e_i in $M(K_{1,n})$ and the vertices v, e_1, e_2, \dots, e_n induce a clique of order $n + 1$ in $M(K_{1,n})$. i.e $V(M(K_{1,n})) = \{v\} \cup \{v_i : 1 \leq i \leq n\} \cup \{e_i : 1 \leq i \leq n\}$. Hence $n + 1$ distinct colors are required to color the vertices v, e_1, e_2, \dots, e_n . Note that e_i is the only external private neighbour of v_i with respect to any set $S \subseteq V$. Therefore we assign the color which is different from the already assigned colors to v_i . Hence $\chi_{ioir}(M(K_{1,n})) \geq n + 2$. Assign *ioir*-coloring as follows: For $1 \leq i \leq n$, assign the color c_i for e_i and assign the color c_{n+1} to v . For $1 \leq i \leq n$, assign the color c_{n+2} to all the vertices v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n . Hence $\chi_{ioir}(M(K_{1,n})) \leq n + 2$.

(ii) By the definition of central graph, each edge vv_i in $K_{1,n}$ is subdivided by the vertex e_i in $C(K_{1,n})$ and the vertices v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n induce a clique of order n in $C(K_{1,n})$. i.e $V(C(K_{1,n})) = \{v\} \cup \{v_i : 1 \leq i \leq n\} \cup \{e_i : 1 \leq i \leq n\}$. Since v_i ($1 \leq i \leq n$) induce a clique of order n , we have $\chi_{ioir}(C(K_{1,n})) \geq n$. We now prove that $\chi_{ioir}(C(K_{1,n})) \geq n + 1$. Suppose $\chi_{ioir}(C(K_{1,n})) = n$. Let V_i be the set of vertices which are colored with c_i , $i = 1$ to n . Let we assign the color c_i to v_i ($1 \leq i \leq n$) and assign the color c_1 to v . Therefore the vertices e_1, e_2, \dots, e_n are colored by $c_2, c_3, \dots, c_{n-1}, c_n$ in some arrangement. Hence at least two of the vertices e_i and e_j are colored with the same color c_m . Clearly any vertex adjacent to vertices e_i and e_j is also joined to vertex of color c_m . It follows that there is no external private neighbour for the vertices e_i and e_j with respect to V_m . This is a contradiction. Hence $\chi_{ioir}(C(K_{1,n})) \geq n + 1$. Assign *ioir*-coloring as follows: For $1 \leq i \leq n$, assign the color c_i for v_i and assign the color c_{n+1} for each e_i . Finally we assign the color c_1 to v . Hence $\chi_{ioir}(C(K_{1,n})) \leq n + 1$.

(iii) By the definition of total graph, we have $V(T(K_{1,n})) = \{v\} \cup \{v_i : 1 \leq i \leq n\} \cup \{e_i : 1 \leq i \leq n\}$, in which the vertices v, e_1, e_2, \dots, e_n induce a clique of order $n + 1$. Clearly $\chi_{ioir}(T(K_{1,n})) \geq n + 1$. Let we assign the color c_i to e_i ($1 \leq i \leq n$) and assign the color c_{n+1} to v . Since e_i and v are the external private neighbors of v_i with respect to V_i and V_{n+1} , we need one more color to v_i . Hence $\chi_{ioir}(T(K_{1,n})) \geq n + 2$. Assign *ioir*-coloring as follows: For $1 \leq i \leq n$, assign the color c_i for e_i and assign the color c_{n+1} to v . Finally we assign the color c_{n+2} to each v_i . Hence $\chi_{ioir}(T(K_{1,n})) \leq n + 2$.

(iv) Since $L(K_{1,n}) \cong K_n$, $\chi_{ioir}(L(K_{1,n})) = n$. \square

Proposition 3.2 For any double star graph $K_{1,n,n}$, we have

$$\chi_{ioir}(M(K_{1,n,n})) = \begin{cases} n+1 & \forall n \geq 3 \\ 4 & n = 2 \end{cases}$$

Proof Clearly we observe that $\chi_{ioir}(M(K_{1,2,2})) = 4$. By the definition of middle graph, each edge vv_i and v_iu_i ($1 \leq i \leq n$) in $K_{1,n,n}$ are subdivided by the vertices e_i and s_i in $M(K_{1,n,n})$ and the vertices v, e_1, e_2, \dots, e_n induce a clique of order $n+1$ (say K_{n+1}) in $M(K_{1,n,n})$. i.e $V(M(K_{1,n,n})) = \{v\} \cup \{v_i : 1 \leq i \leq n\} \cup \{u_i : 1 \leq i \leq n\} \cup \{e_i : 1 \leq i \leq n\} \cup \{s_i : 1 \leq i \leq n\}$. Clearly $\chi_{ioir}(M(K_{1,n,n})) \geq n+1$. Assign *ioir*-coloring as follows: For $1 \leq i \leq n$, assign the color c_i for e_i and assign the color c_{n+1} to v . For $1 \leq i \leq n$, assign two distinct colors c_l and c_m other than c_{n+1} and c_i to the vertices v_i and s_i . Finally, assign the color c_{n+1} to each u_i ($1 \leq i \leq n$). Let V_i be the set of vertices which are colored with c_i , $i = 1$ to $n+1$. Note that v is the external private neighbor of all the vertices e_i with respect to V_i , $1 \leq i \leq n$ and e_i 's are the external private neighbors of v with respect to V_{n+1} . For $1 \leq i \leq n$, s_i is the external private neighbor of u_i and v_i with respect to V_{n+1} and V_i . Finally, v_i is the external private neighbor of s_i with respect to V_m . Hence $\chi_{ioir}(M(K_{1,n,n})) \leq n+1$. \square

Proposition 3.3 For any double star graph $K_{1,n,n}$, we have $\chi_{ioir}(C(K_{1,n,n})) = n+2$.

Proof By the definition of central graph, each edge vv_i and v_iu_i ($1 \leq i \leq n$) in $K_{1,n,n}$ are subdivided by the vertices e_i and s_i in $C(K_{1,n,n})$. The vertices v, u_1, u_2, \dots, u_n induce a clique of order $n+1$ (say K_{n+1}) and the vertices v_i ($1 \leq i \leq n$) induce a clique of order n in $C(K_{1,n,n})$. i.e $V(C(K_{1,n,n})) = \{v\} \cup \{v_i : 1 \leq i \leq n\} \cup \{u_i : 1 \leq i \leq n\} \cup \{e_i : 1 \leq i \leq n\} \cup \{s_i : 1 \leq i \leq n\}$. Clearly $\chi_{ioir}(C(K_{1,n,n})) \geq n+1$. We now prove that $\chi_{ioir}(C(K_{1,n,n})) \geq n+2$. Suppose $\chi_{ioir}(C(K_{1,n,n})) = n+1$. Since v, u_i ($1 \leq i \leq n$) induce a clique of order $n+1$, let us assign the color c_{n+1} to v and assign the color c_i to u_i ($1 \leq i \leq n$). Since e_i has degree 2 and v is adjacent to the vertex of color c_i $\forall i$, v_i is the only external private neighbour of e_i . But v_i is adjacent to the vertex of color c_j , $\forall j \neq i$. Therefore e_i must be colored only with c_i and v_i must be colored only with c_{n+1} . Since v_i ($1 \leq i \leq n$) induce a clique of order n , it leads to a contradiction. Hence $\chi_{ioir}(C(K_{1,n,n})) \geq n+2$. Consider the colors c_1, c_2, \dots, c_{n+2} . Assign *ioir*-coloring as follows: Assign the colour c_{n+1} to v and assign the color c_i to u_i , where $1 \leq i \leq n$. Assign the color c_{n+1} to all the vertices s_1, s_2, \dots, s_n and assign the color c_{n+2} to all the vertices e_1, e_2, \dots, e_n . Finally, we assign the color c_i to v_i for $1 \leq i \leq n$. Let V_i be the set of vertices which are colored with c_i , $i = 1$ to $n+2$. For $1 \leq i \leq n$, e_i is the external private neighbor of v with respect to V_{n+1} and v_i is the external private neighbor of e_i with respect to V_{n+2} . For $1 \leq i \leq n$, e_i is the external private neighbor of v_i with respect to V_i and v_i is the external private neighbor of s_i with respect to V_{n+1} . Finally, v is the external private neighbor of all the vertices u_i with respect to V_i . Hence $\chi_{ioir}(C(K_{1,n,n})) \leq n+2$. \square

Proposition 3.4 For any double star graph $K_{1,n,n}$, we have $\chi_{ioir}(T(K_{1,n,n})) = n+1$.

Proof By the definition of total graph, we have $V(T(K_{1,n,n})) = \{v\} \cup \{v_i : 1 \leq i \leq n\} \cup$

$\{u_i : 1 \leq i \leq n\} \cup \{e_i : 1 \leq i \leq n\} \cup \{s_i : 1 \leq i \leq n\}$ in which the vertices v, e_1, e_2, \dots, e_n induce a clique of order $n + 1$. Clearly $\chi_{ioir}(T(K_{1,n,n})) \geq n + 1$. Consider the colors c_1, c_2, \dots, c_{n+1} . Assign *ioir*-coloring as follows: Assign the color c_{n+1} to v and assign the colour c_i to e_i , where $1 \leq i \leq n$. For $1 \leq i \leq n$, assign two distinct colors other than c_{n+1} and c_i to the vertices v_i and s_i . Finally, assign the color c_{n+1} to each $u_i (1 \leq i \leq n)$. Hence $\chi_{ioir}(T(K_{1,n,n})) \leq n + 1$. \square

Proposition 3.5 For any double star graph $K_{1,n,n}$, we have $\chi_{ioir}(L(K_{1,n,n})) = n + 1$.

Proof By the definition of line graph, each edge of $K_{1,n,n}$ taken to be as vertex in $(L(K_{1,n,n}))$. The vertices e_1, e_2, \dots, e_n induce a clique of order n and the vertices s_1, s_2, \dots, s_n are all pendant in $(L(K_{1,n,n}))$. i.e $V(L(K_{1,n,n})) = \{e_i : 1 \leq i \leq n\} \cup \{s_i : 1 \leq i \leq n\}$. From Theorem 2.10, we have $\chi_{ioir}(L(K_{1,n,n})) \geq n + 1$. Assign *ioir*-coloring as follows: Assign the color c_{n+1} to all the vertices s_i , where $1 \leq i \leq n$ and assign the color c_i to e_i , where $1 \leq i \leq n$. Hence $\chi_{ioir}(L(K_{1,n,n})) \leq n + 1$. \square

References

- [1] S. Arumugam, K. Raja Chandrasekar and S. Sudha, Irredundant and open irredundant colorings of graphs, *Bulletin of the ICA*, (61)(2011), 24-36.
- [2] G. Chartrand and L. Lesniak, *Graphs and Digraphs* (4th Edition), CRC, 2005.
- [3] E.J. Cockayne, Generalized irredundance in graphs: hereditary and Ramsey numbers, *J. Combin. Math. Combin. Comput.*, 31(1999), 15-31.
- [4] E.J. Cockayne and S. Finbow, Generalized irredundance in graphs: Nordhaus-Gaddum bounds, *Discuss. Math. Graph Theory* (To appear).
- [5] S. Finbow, *Generalization of Irredundance in Graphs*, Ph.D thesis, University of Victoria, 2003.
- [6] T.W. Haynes, S.T. Hedetniemi and P.J. Slater, *Fundamentals of Domination in Graphs*, Marcel Dekker, Inc., New York, (1998).
- [7] T.W. Haynes, S.T. Hedetniemi and P.J. Slater, *Domination in Graphs-Advanced Topics*, Marcel Dekker, Inc., New York, (1998).
- [8] T.W. Haynes, S.T. Hedetniemi, S.M. Hedetniemi, A.A. McRae and P.J. Slater, Irredundant colorings of graphs, *Bulletin of the ICA*, 54(2008), 103-121.
- [9] S.T. Hedetniemi, Unsolved algorithmic problems on trees, *AKCE J. Graphs. Combin.*, 3, No 2 (2006), 1-37.
- [10] M. Venkatachalam, J. Vernold Vivin and K. Kaliraj, Harmonious coloring on double star graph families, *Tamkang Journal of Mathematics*, 2(43)(2012), 153-158.
- [11] J. Vernold Vivin, K. Thilagavathi and B. Anitha, On harmonious coloring of line graph of central graphs of bipartite graphs, *Journal of Combinatorics, Information and System Sciences*, No.1-4(combined) 32(2007), 233-240.
- [12] J. Vernold Vivin and K. Thilagavathi, On harmonious coloring of line graph of central graph of paths, *Applied Mathematical Sciences*, no.5 3(2009), 205-214.
- [13] J. Vernold Vivin: Ph.D thesis, *Harmonious Coloring of Total Graphs, n-leaf, Central graphs and Circumdetic Graphs*, Bharathiar University, Coimbatore, 2007.